

Co-designing pilot games with citizens and policy stakeholders to increase climate action

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Abstract—This paper presents an initial report on the co-design processes between researchers and policy stakeholders in the GREAT (Games Realizing Effective and Affective Transformation) project applied in the context of the climate emergency. The objective of piloting these co-design processes is to develop a methodology to support policy stakeholders in identifying and determining an urgent climate issue. We engage stakeholders in co-design of games-based activities, which can be instantiated for citizens and simultaneously be used to collect their attitudes towards climate policies. By piloting these co-design processes, we aim to support policy stakeholders in identifying an urgent climate issue they want to address. Based on this climate issue, we co-design games-based interventions which provide the opportunity for citizens to engage with policy issues, and to represent their attitudes and preferences relating to climate policies. We develop two types of game-based methods - a short quiz format embedded in a mobile game, and longer, collaborative serious games - for collecting, analyzing, and presenting data on citizens' attitudes to policymakers for improving climate policies. In this paper, we describe the pilot studies undertaken and discuss the lessons learnt.

Keywords—games, climate emergency, transformation, citizen science, societal impact, sustainable development goals

I. INTRODUCTION

The growth of games on computers and mobile platforms is a remarkable phenomenon of recent years, raising important questions about the cultural role and meaning of games, and the potential social purposes which they can serve. It is in this context that the GREAT project (Games Realizing Effective and Affective Transformation) [1] is framed by three major social issues. First, although the digital games industry is now a larger economic sector than either music or film, estimated to have generated \$180.3 billion in 2021 [2], there is no consensus on the nature of the impact of games on society, nor even if this is good or bad. Second, in a parallel process since the mid-1990s, the proportion of

citizens who are “dissatisfied” with democracy in their countries has risen by almost 10 percentage points globally, particularly in high-income democracies [3]. Similarly, the United Nations [4] consider that trust in news sources and scientists is at an all-time low. Dissatisfaction and mistrust correlate with skepticism, and it is a necessity to build trust, thereby reinforcing democracy [5]. The GREAT project leverages the potential of games to reach and engage a large proportion of world citizens in order to tackle the current global challenges (such as the climate emergency) to influence policy-making, and aims to:

1. Establish ways in which games can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy-makers.
2. Understand the actual and potential impact that games have on citizens' engagement in social issues and challenges, and on policy stakeholders' awareness of citizens' attitudes.
3. Assess the benefits and risks to individuals and society of using games to promote engagement with societal challenges.
4. Provide practical guidance for games developments and policy stakeholders.

In this paper, we summarize the pilot studies carried out to date to gain our first insights into achieving the above-listed objectives, in particular 1-3. We particularly focus on those studies that contributed to the development of a methodology for co-designing games. The pilot studies were all conducted using a standardized approach, and each addressed a subset of the eight participatory steps in the GREAT case study cycle [6]. We describe some of the pilots below together with the results obtained. The GREAT project consortium consists of two commercial game companies (one specializing in short quizzes embedded in popular mobile games, and the other in longer collaborative serious games

addressing dilemmas), five European academic partners, and 2 associate partners in China and South Africa, respectively.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, we provide a short literature review on the use of mobile game apps, which were developed for users to learn and gain more awareness of sustainability issues. Our planned dilemma games have an educational aspect, and are designed for learners to learn about the different consequences of various actions taken in the context of climate issues and policies. Similarly, embedded quiz games can raise awareness and curiosity about environmental issues. To the best of our knowledge, no similar research is currently being carried out which uses embedded quiz games and serious games to engage citizens in identifying appropriate policies for addressing a policy challenge such as climate change. However, related work has been carried out in technology-supported methods for facilitating sustainability education.

A mobile game app developed by Gatti *et al.* [7] focuses on business sustainability education, addressing corporate sustainability issues by utilizing an action learning approach via simulation and gaming. Their results suggest that these approaches successfully generated and increased cognitive and affective learning outcomes, which could positively aid the development of critical thinking skills in learners and significantly increase their motivation. The results suggest that the game was effective in influencing students' expertise in the subject and their attitudes, causing a behavioral change towards sustainability. This was especially true if a student recorded a high level of motivation to attend the course and showed interest in the subject, before he/she started using the game app. More specifically, the game app allowed students to understand the complexity and variety of sustainability-related issues and influenced a change in attitudes and behavioral intentions concerning sustainability-related issues.

A similar exploratory study of sustainability learning through gaming was carried out by Fabricatore and Lopez [8]. Through the game, learners created a 'spirit' of inquiry to help them simulate, explore and reflect on different scenarios which then challenged them to develop the competencies and skills targeted by the game, such as communication and negotiation skills. The theme of sustainability is integral to this game, and its development was informed by complex systems thinking. It addresses language issues, specific user needs such as disabilities, geographical barriers and access to technology.

Additionally, a number of games and gamified apps have been created that target sustainability learning and climate change mitigation, as discussed in the review by Douglas *et al.* [9]. They conclude that these apps show greater promise in generating and influencing citizens' behavioral change than apps without gamified aspects and only by providing information alone. It was noted that "gamification can lead to longer-term psychological engagement than other behavioral change methods such as nudging" [8]. Another

gamification system in art education for learning sustainable development targeting primary school students was created by Bogdanic & Vuk [10]. The results showed that students were interested and their attitudes towards environmental protection were increased as a result of playing the game, e.g. doing tasks such as recycling objects.

A number of advanced technologies (such as artificial intelligence/generative artificial intelligence technologies, game-based learning approaches, gamification techniques, extended reality & social media technologies) and simple technologies (such as radio, SMS) have been deployed in various community settings to facilitate education for sustainable development and to advance sustainable development goals. For example, within the UNESCO Global Network of Learning Cities, a number of publications have been published since 2013 which examine the key features of learning cities and the ways that lifelong learning can be facilitated. This applies especially to youth and adults focusing on inclusive learning environments and fostering diversity including target groups such as learners with disabilities and/or special needs, girls and women, indigenous communities and displaced persons [11]. In particular, a learning city defined by UNESCO [11] is as follows:

"A Learning City is a city which effectively mobilize its resources in every sector to

- 1. promote inclusive learning from basic to higher education;*
- 2. re-vitalise learning in families and communities;*
- 3. facilitate learning for and in the workplace;*
- 4. extend the use of modern learning technologies;*
- 5. enhance quality and excellence in learning; and*
- 6. foster a culture of learning throughout life. In so doing it will create and reinforce individual empowerment and social cohesion, economic and cultural prosperity, and sustainable development."*

Currently, 356 member states belong to the Global Network of Learning Cities, including 64 cities from 35 countries that joined in February 2024. They include Manchester (England), Dresden (Germany), Cerdanyola del Valles (Spain), Recife (Brazil), Merida (Mexico), Sumy (Ukraine), Ho Chi Minh City (Vietnam), Nanjing (China), Muscat (Oman), Fes (Morocco), Alexandria (Egypt) and Dakar (Senegal). Currently, 79 countries host UNESCO learning cities and by 2030, the global community seeks to provide lifelong learning opportunities for all and make cities sustainable. The requirement for a city to join the network is the commitment of the municipality to provide lifelong learning in the spirit of the values and objectives named above, in the definition of a Learning City.

The research deployed in the GREAT project supports cities in becoming Learning Cities at the local level, addressing points 4 and 6 of UNESCO's definition above. The project addresses point 4 of the definition, above, by extending the use and area of application of "modern technologies" in its work with games. Regarding point 6, GREAT utilizes games-based activities to enhance citizen engagement and individual empowerment, as well as social

cohesion, economic and cultural prosperity, and finally contributing to the sustainable development goals including increasing climate action.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND LIMITATIONS

The project objectives determine the types of participants to be invited to the co-design activities including workshops, i.e. citizens and policymakers. Due to time limitations in the pilot stage, it was decided to invite internal project participants or participants from our network of connections. The studies were designed to shed light on methods for reaching co-design decisions, and on activities with participants to co-design games in the main case studies to be implemented in further project phases. The research methodology utilized in this project is the case study design methods and process, which are further explained in [6]. This design incorporates an instantiated eight-stage process, which provides implementation detail for all stages of the case study process. We now characterize the work carried out by describing some of the principal pilot studies, while a full report will be provided in a subsequent article. The participant information is shown in the table below:

Step	Date	Stakeholders	No. of participants (M/F)	Location
1	22/03 /2023	The Green Party	9 (4F / 5M)	Frankfurt, Germany & online
1	25-26/10 / 2023	Urban Gorillas	1 (1F)	Nicosia, Cyprus
2	21/06 /2023	The Green Party	4 (2F / 2M)	Frankfurt, Germany & online
2	15/11 /2023	Urban Gorillas	2 (2F)	Nicosia, Cyprus
3	15/06 /2023	Internal dilemma game design	3 (3F)	Vienna, Austria & online
3	17/11 /2023	Urban Gorillas	2 (1F 1M)	Nicosia, Cyprus / online

In the future main case studies, which are beyond the scope of this paper, random sampling techniques will be used where possible, to ensure as far as we can that each member of the population has an equal chance of being included in the sample.

IV. PILOT STUDY 1 – CONSULTATION WITH STAKEHOLDERS

The first step of the research cycle consists of **facilitating the prioritization of climate topics together with the stakeholders**. Given the context, there may be multiple climate issues that stakeholders would like to explore, however, for the purpose of the study, there is a need to focus on one or two of the most urgent issues that can be further explored together with citizens. During an initial workshop with the Green Party in Frankfurt, two topics were identified as most urgent by the participants: 1) *traffic and mobility, priority for cycle lanes*, and 2) *building infrastructure (social housing, schools, ...) without sealing green spaces*. Note that this discussion took place with politicians in the city Frankfurt Am Main, Germany, which is a major financial hub, having a significant number of cars, extensive public transportation system, and both office and residential buildings with limited green spaces.

In the second step and as part of the initial workshop, we **determined what the game-based activities will achieve and how**. Project researchers collaborated with the stakeholders to define 1) *specific dilemmas requiring information on citizens’ attitudes, which are important for politicians to know about*, 2) *the expected insight and evidence which can be offered to policy-makers*, 3) *the specific target groups and their roles*, and 4) *how data will be gathered, analyzed and delivered to stakeholders*. The politicians in this case strongly advocated for citizen engagement via the methods proposed by our project. Nevertheless, they did not have an immediate need for the proposed activities in terms of a specific dilemma experienced by a specific organization or group regarding an urgent climate issue. As a result, some of the conversations centered on the creation of a better process for better engagement and communication with citizens, who have different expectations and may not be familiar with politics or administration, or who do not get involved until they are personally affected. This is particularly true for marginalized people, often young, who do not have interest groups representing them. There was also a consensus that there is a lack of information for citizens concerning what policies have been decided and implemented and awareness of these processes. These views strongly validate the game-based approach to elicit citizens’ attitudes taken in our GREAT project, as citizens may otherwise be unwilling to engage in political processes via the usual channels. The GREAT project offers two alternative channels.

Firstly, one of our commercial partners. Playmob has expertise in the use of short 1-minute quizzes, which can be inserted in popular mobile games in collaborations which may involve payment to the games companies. These can reach a potential of up to 3 million citizens worldwide to gauge their attitudes towards specific climate policies, forming a large amount of quantitative data. Facilitated by the expertise of our other commercial games partner, Serious Games Interactive, longer collaborative dilemma games can

be deployed to gain qualitative data, which can support and complement the quantitative data collected. A few hundred citizen participants in the dilemma games are expected in our three-year project. Both of these types of data form the basis of citizens' climate attitudes, which will be anonymized, analyzed, summarized and transferred to the relevant policy-makers, primarily in Europe (and potentially in China and South Africa).

The *lessons learnt* from these two workshops were that the policy stakeholders have ***an urgent need for citizen engagement on a particular urgent issue, which can benefit from the use of game-based approaches to reach and engage them.***

V. PILOT STUDY 2 – CO-DESIGN 1 (DILEMMA GAME)

Following the insights from the politician stakeholders gained in pilot study 1, we proceeded further to co-design the game elements e.g., the *short quizzes* and the *game logic of a dilemma game*. Our Vienna project partner had the ambition to design a dilemma game, based on a real dilemma relating to traffic and housing in Vienna, which addressed a similar issue to the one discussed in the Frankfurt pilot study. This activity therefore combined the outcomes already achieved in Frankfurt, while preparing an exemplar for a possible future case study in Vienna. This pilot study was conducted internally by our Vienna project partner and commercial games partner specialized in long collaborative dilemma games.

The two different types of game-based tools (short quiz vs long dilemma) serve different purposes. For example, the quiz games may help in raising citizens' awareness of societal challenges and their participation in the quiz can collaboratively contribute to climate policies more suited to them. On the other hand, specific urgent climate issues can be transferred to a dilemma game, where citizens spend significantly more time to brainstorm about different aspects of the identified climate issues and it is possible to view different consequences of various actions taken in the created dilemma games. Due to the nature of the two different types of games, it was commented by our internal team members that it could be beneficial to first co-design the dilemma game to elicit in-depth details concerning the climate issue, and then using the questions formed in this game to inform the questions used in the quiz game, to extend the reach of citizens' engagement.

The *lessons learnt* from this co-design workshop related to the challenges of formulating the logic, which would translate the identified dilemma into a game with various options that would trigger people's opinions. As the academic partner's design process became blocked, our commercial games partner was consulted and they proposed a draft design as well as a template of the game. We learnt that it is not a simple task to transfer a question or dilemma into a serious game logic. It is a substantial challenge to involve people (project researchers or stakeholders) in this activity, if they are not experienced in game design, and it takes time and experience to implement the dilemma game logic. It was necessary and important to receive support from a professional to transfer the story into a coherent dilemma

game. It is recommended that any co-design activities with stakeholders should only be carried out with a very limited number of people. An alternative approach is for the commercial games partner to make a first draft in collaboration with pilot facilitators, based on the input from the stakeholders. This can then be presented to the stakeholders and modified subject to their further input.

VI. PILOT STUDY 3 – CO-DESIGN 2 (DILEMMA GAME)

Building on the previous study, we started a new collaboration with an interested stakeholder, a non-profit organization called Urban Gorillas based in Nicosia, Cyprus, who envision healthy, creative, and socially inclusive cities. Their motivation to collaborate with our project is to test a potential policy that focuses on the greening of privately multi-owned rooftops and the incentives that could be offered to citizens. Urban Gorillas are members of the European Creative Rooftop Network (ECRN), which is co-financed by the European Commission and the Ministry of Education and Culture in Cyprus. More specifically, Urban Gorillas would like to test this policy with two specific groups in Nicosia – 1) architects, planners, designers, engineers, and 2) building owners, contractors and developers. This organization had in mind the policy that they wanted to 'test' with citizens and had already many ideas and strategies relating to the dimensions in the dilemma game. In particular, they were interested in repurposing and greening of rooftops as an action that contributes to climate neutrality. Urban Gorillas already work with experts in the target field, such as the Cyprus Energy Agency, but the GREAT pilot study was interesting because it facilitated an understanding of citizens' perspectives on and reactions to the approach and potential policies to support it..

The dilemma game co-design workshop identified 1) *lists of incentives for rooftop repurposing*, 2) *a list of resources to support policy development*, and 3) *a list of barriers to rooftop usage*. It was decided that the following potential groups would be invited to participate in the games – homeowners, building developers, management companies, architects, people who rent accommodation / potential buyers, neighbors. A minimum of 8 participants and a maximum of 50 participants would be required to participate in each dilemma game. The playfulness of the activity was emphasized to encourage active and natural participation, and circumvent the use of the words 'climate change' to avoid participants coming to the activity with a preconceived set of attitudes which could distort their response to the specific dilemma.

This game is currently under development and includes a role-play aspect, for example, types of owners (family, single, older couple, residents that live in different parts of the building). For example, if current apartment owners are participants, valuable feedback regarding how they would feel about using the roofs can be obtained. The proposal of an incentive can then be introduced and the response to it documented. A questionnaire can be added at the end, to gather further ideas from the participants. Specific dilemmas will inform the role-play elements of the game including:

1. One person lives on the top floor, but another lives on the ground floor that already has a private garden. Should the incentives be the same?
2. Should access be allowed for all residents, even if they do not agree with the initiative?
3. Would a tax reduction be a fair effective motivation for participation in an initiative with benefits for all, or would it unfairly benefit the recipients?

This workshop covered step 3 of our co-design process [6], namely **collaborative design of game activities**, and step 4 is expected to be carried out shortly, namely **game activities with case study participants**. Thereafter, step 5 of the participatory research approach is to perform **collaborative data analysis** with citizens, also known as a *public data sprint* [12].

VII. EVALUATION AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT

In this section, we briefly discuss the upcoming activities which will support us in the evaluation and impact assessment of the project activities. We will evaluate the scientific, socio-economic, and participant-level impact that the games have achieved in terms of stakeholder engagement, impact on climate policies, and the social use and cultural value of games. We have created a comprehensive evaluation framework including distinct methodologies to assess the three dimensions of impact:

- **Scientific impact:** we will monitor the dissemination and application of the project's scientific outputs (datasets, publications, materials) on academic and general media channels to gauge scientific impact. Further, we will collect qualitative data for in-depth information through a) workshops with project partners, and b) qualitative interviews with experts in the field.
- **Socio-economic impact:** economic impact will be assessed with a range of indicators covering target groups reached, development of features, and exchange with non-research partners. In-depth understanding of the project's societal impact will be gained through qualitative interviews with policy stakeholders.
- **Participant-level impact:** we will assess participants involved in our game-based tools and participatory workshops using pre- and post-questionnaires, structured focus groups, and debriefing reflections using quantitative and qualitative prompts.

Our main case studies are currently in development and the impact assessment of these will be presented in future project publications. Step 6 of the research cycle is **policy conclusions & evaluation**, Step 7 is **community engagement** via social media, presentations & webinar, and obtaining feedback from stakeholders. Lastly, Step 8 is

policy stakeholder engagement including preparing insight reports for policy-makers, plan engagement with and present results to policy-makers.

VIII. CONCLUDING REMARKS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we presented our games-based approach in citizen engagement in the context of the climate emergency and as a tool for collecting citizens' attitudes towards different climate policies. We employed a participatory methodology involving citizens and policy stakeholders in game design and data analysis. Two types of games are deployed in our project – 1) *short 1-minute quizzes*, shown as ads in popular mobile games to reach a total of up to 3 million citizens worldwide throughout our project, and 2) *longer collaborative dilemma games*, which involve participants in longer discussions but can elicit in-depth qualitative data concerning citizens' attitudes and the nuanced reasons for supporting different solutions for climate issues. Additionally, both types of game-based tools have the potential to raise citizens' awareness on urgent global issues / emergencies and to increase their understanding of the sustainability issues, sustainable development goals and specifically climate change education.

Three pilot studies of our project were presented with lessons learnt and recommendations for participatory researchers, supporting the implementation of citizen science methods to engage citizens in other subjects including sustainable development and beyond.

Our case study as project methodology in the primary research instrument deployed in the GREAT project [6]. It is written to support consortium partners in undertaking research activities in the project as its primary audience. However, it is anticipated that due to the scalable nature of the design that future design iterations could inform upcoming case study research in digital domains involving citizen science and where citizen agency is a primary objective. Using this case study design approach may also mean that not all of the conducted case studies will be required to conduct all stages of the process. Though, cumulatively all stages will be implemented and evaluated over the sum of the GREAT case studies undertaken over the project duration.

Our future intended sample size is large ($n = \sim 300,000$) and thereby will enable and enhance the generalizability of findings to the broader population. We will incorporate measures to include diversity in our samples and hence additionally strive to capture a range of perspectives and characteristics of citizens informing us of their attitudes towards climate policies.

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